

BASIC MECHANISMS FOR THE FORMATION OF A LEGAL PERSON

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Abstract. *The article focuses on how individuals become legal persons. It examines the development and progression of legal culture, political and psychological consciousness, and most importantly, legal consciousness. The article argues that legal knowledge should be transformed into values, acquire an emotional aspect, and become ingrained beliefs, and habitual behavior to serve as a real motivator and regulator of proper conduct. Furthermore, it suggests that individuals can only establish a solid foundation for their legal culture through proper legal socialization.*

Keywords: *legal person, culture, legal socialization, legal consciousness, legal understanding, internalization.*

INTRODUCTION

Human life in society is governed by both written and unwritten laws. Learning these laws, understanding legal principles, and knowing how to behave appropriately are all part of the process of legal socialization. It also involves developing necessary social skills, being aware of one's rights, and understanding how to exercise them. Becoming a responsible citizen is a result of long-term interaction with the society.

Throughout history, humanity has developed numerous social ideas and projects that have played a crucial role in social progress and the liberation of individuals. Many of these initiatives have contributed to the humanistic development of legal relations in society. One such concept is the theory of legal socialization, which has evolved through various stages since its inception in the 1960s. Initially, researchers did not make a clear distinction between the processes of political and legal socialization of individuals. Their primary focus was on establishing a system of values that shape human political consciousness.

During the 1970s, the study of legal socialization gained prominence alongside political socialization. Two main approaches emerged during this time to explore the formation of legal values and human behavior. The first approach, rooted in the theory of cognitive development, emphasized the importance of cognitive differences in legal thinking as the primary factor in an individual's evolution as a legal subject. The second approach, based on social learning theory, focused on the influence of the external socio-legal environment on an individual's legal socialization. In the early stages of the individual-oriented cognitive development theory, psychologists Tapp J. L. and Levine F. J. made significant contributions. The fundamental idea of the theory was that the success of legal socialization is closely linked to the level of maturity of legal thinking, which progresses through three main stages of cognitive evolution.

As already noted, there are three ways to assimilate legal culture (rules of law and legal values) in the process of socialization:

1) objective method, when a person, in the process of one or another activity, interacting with other persons, learns the appropriate course of action, or pattern of behavior;

2) the traditional way, when a person, observing the actions of people in various situations, learns the appropriate way of behavior;

3) a rational way, when a person learns about legal values, and standards of legal behavior from conversations with other people, from reading books, from media channels.

It should be noted that the process of assimilation of legal norms and standards of legal behavior proceeds sequentially, according to life cycles, and stages of individual socialization.

RESULTS

The process of legal socialization involves three main aspects. Firstly, it includes understanding the criteria for evaluating legally significant situations. Secondly, it involves studying laws and rules independently of oneself. Thirdly, it entails learning how to apply these rules. In essence, an individual needs not only to comprehend the specific laws that apply in society but also relate them to themselves. This means understanding how the laws affect them, what they are permitted and not permitted to do, the potential consequences for breaking the laws, and how to protect their legal rights.

From a very early age, children start to absorb the first elements of legal culture. They engage in activities, acquire skills, and assimilate standards of normative and evaluative behavior. They first encounter legal ideas through fairy tales, develop concepts about the functions of law and its representatives through role-playing games, and gradually form a primitive but personal understanding of legal life. As they grow older, they expand their circle of contacts and engage in more complex activities, their awareness in various spheres, including the legal sphere, becomes enriched and developed.

DISCUSSION

The main purpose of legal socialization is to promote lawful behavior by fostering a comprehensive legal education and legal consciousness in individuals. Legal awareness is linked to the process of socialization in two main ways.

Firstly, an individual's life experiences and interactions influence their attitudes, relationships, and values in the legal domain. Their legal consciousness, including their awareness of the law, assessment of legal reality, and motivation for lawful behavior, depends on their social connections, degree of integration into the legal culture of society, and involvement in social groups that affect the assimilation of legal information.

Secondly, legal consciousness not only reflects a person's legal experiences but also motivates their behavior. Shaped by external influences, legal consciousness guides individuals' actions and directs them toward finding optimal resolutions to legal situations, essentially serving as a regulator of behavior.

Legal awareness, as a component of individual consciousness, comprises three elements: intellectual (cognitive), evaluative (emotional), and behavioral (emotional-volitional). The cognitive element is characterized by the accumulation of legal knowledge and skills. The evaluative element consists of value judgments and attitudes towards the rules of law (positive, indifferent, negative). The behavioral element presupposes an inclination towards lawful behavior, a habit of unconditionally complying with the rules of law, and an intolerant attitude towards their violation.

In the process of legal socialization, a person can develop legal consciousness through the influence of various social factors and personal characteristics. Legal consciousness can exist at both cognitive and evaluative levels.

At the cognitive level, legal consciousness is seen as the sum of legal knowledge. However, having this knowledge does not always guarantee lawful behavior. For example, a person may be fully aware of the law but choose to violate it.

At the evaluative level, in addition to knowing the law, a person also evaluates it positively. Nevertheless, even this does not always ensure lawful behavior. A person may feel tempted to break the law for personal gain or experience pressure from an asocial group, leading them to act unlawfully.

Legal knowledge must transform into deeply held values, have an emotional impact, become internal convictions, and manifest as habitual behavior to truly encourage lawful conduct. The formation of legal consciousness, just like general consciousness and personality, begins in childhood and throughout the school years. Family and school play crucial roles as the primary agents of legal socialization.

The main psychological mechanism for the development of legal consciousness in children and adolescents is personification, where moral and legal values and the law are embodied by parental figures. Children learn appropriate behavior and model social conduct based on their parents. The degree and depth of assimilation of these behavioral patterns and moral and legal attitudes greatly depend on child's attitude towards specific individuals, such as their parents, who embody certain value orientations.

When children has a positive emotional attitude towards their parents and later towards teachers, they learn not only the specific content of the communication process, but also their attitude towards objects, phenomena, their way of thinking, worldview, habits, tastes, and even the gait through emotional transfer. The moral and legal values of the parents and teachers are also learned and adopted, contributing to the formation of basic moral and legal categories, the concept of good and evil, and the idea of justice.

Conversely, when a child has a negative attitude towards their parents and teachers, they reject not only the individuals but also the system of moral and legal values they represent. This can lead to a reorientation towards other individuals with different, often contrasting, values. Legal socialization encompasses not only the formation of ideas about proper and normative behavior but also the development of ideas about one's rights. Moreover, in the process of interacting with parents, peers, and adults, a child appeals to certain moral standards and a sense of justice, which they feel but may not yet be able to formulate.

In its most concentrated form, the sphere of moral and legal relations in a child is associated with the concept of justice in a situation where what is proper clashes with what is desired. The behavior of adults in such situations is very instructive. It is known that some kindergarten teachers, parents, and elementary school teachers do not always consider it necessary or simply do not want to "understand" children's conflicts. They are unfairly strict with some and undeservedly kind to others. In the eyes of children, this is nothing more than vividly memorable lessons of lawlessness and arbitrariness, which painfully wounds the offended child. If such a frustrating situation is repeated, child's accumulating irritability provokes new conflicts and subsequently can find a way out through crime.

At an older age, an understanding emerges that the rights of the child are fixed by certain laws and traditions of society, which adults (parents, teachers) are obliged to obey, regardless of their personal preferences.

The gradual inclusion of children in various social institutions, particularly through school enrollment, is crucial. For instance, when a child enters school, they begin to understand that their parents are obligated to purchase school supplies not just because the teacher said so, but because it's a general rule for everyone. This helps the child recognize rights as something inherent to a person, irrespective of their relationships with parents, teachers, and other adults.

Several factors determine the speed of legal socialization, including child's intellectual development, microenvironment, and the educational and cultural level of his/her parents. Professional activities also play a significant role in child's legal socialization. For example, a child growing up in a lawyer's family may experience faster and more fruitful legal socialization.

The school plays an important role as an agent of legal socialization. This is achieved through direct legal socialization in special lessons, where students learn about the principles of government, the role and functions of law in society, and the rights and responsibilities of citizens. Additionally, meetings with representatives of law enforcement agencies help explain the need to comply with legal norms and provide examples from judicial investigative practice to illustrate the consequences of non-compliance.

Legal socialization in our country does not end with school. It also takes place at universities, where students learn about the fundamentals of law in depth.

Legal socialization is influenced by many factors. There's a well-known saying that a person is 1/3 a product of their parents, 1/3 a product of other people's influence, and 1/3 a product of their actions. While we can't change all circumstances, we can change our attitude towards them. Encouraging self-development and helping adolescents, youth, and citizens to implement it effectively are important for regulating legal socialization.

In conclusion, a comprehensive analysis of the role of legal socialization in constructing an individual's legal culture shows the mechanism of legal activity and socially useful behavior, as well as the translation of ideas, norms, and values into real legal experience.

The passage emphasizes the interdependent relationship between legal socialization and legal culture in modern society. It highlights that an individual's proper legal socialization is crucial for developing an appropriate level of legal culture. This positive legal culture should be evident in the cognitive, axiological, and behavioral aspects of an individual's actions. Any shortcomings in these areas can lead to a negative or distorted development of an individual's legal culture. The passage also notes the need to modernize society's legal culture, suggesting that key institutions of civil society should be further developed, law-making activities should be optimized, fundamental principles of legal personality should be established, and the legal education system for young people should be modernized.

CONCLUSIONS

What defines a person as a legal entity is the inherent ability to make law possible. This refers to the capacity to be an independent individual who recognizes others as having the same status. Rights are shaped by the idea of an individual who actively exercises their rights, possesses legal awareness and culture, expresses free will, and consciously upholds the principles of the rule of law. The task of political and legal institutions is to implement and maintain legal personality. Cultivating legal attributes and acquiring legal knowledge, skills, and abilities is the process of

forming a legal personality. This process is influenced by two groups of factors: social and personal. As a result, the mechanism of forming a legal personality is determined by two processes: internalization (legal education) and legal socialization. Internalization is a system of legal norms that direct a person toward specific behavioral patterns and restrict their actions within certain boundaries. Society shapes a person not only through norms and judgments but also through legal relationships, which serve as an important regulator of human behavior and a means of educating individuals as legal beings. Socialization occurs in two ways: by translating external social demands into internal motivations for action (interiorization) and by objectifying a person's inner world in their activities, transitioning from expectations, interests, and goals to practical actions for their realization (exteriorization). A legal personality is conscious of having not only rights but also responsibilities. Among these responsibilities, those that compel individuals to defend their rights and act as active legal beings are particularly significant.

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